

Project BioCombs4Nanofibers

D5.6 Video for broader public

Reporting period	from	01.10.2020	to	30.09.2022
Report completed and released		25.03.2022		Jörn Bonse, Karin Schwibbert, Anja M. Richter

1. Goals and Detailed Description

Overall goal: **D5.6 Video for broader public** reports about main results of the **BioCombs4Nanofibers** project and is to be uploaded in social media, for instance YouTube. The partner **BAM** is in charge of organizing and realizing this project deliverable.

BAM is the German Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing. It is a senior scientific and technical institute with responsibility to the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action.

The public video under the motto “*BioCombs4Nanofibers*” presents central project ideas and scientific results that were published in 2020/2021 in gold open access scientific journal articles (peer-reviewed) [1-3]. These articles all reflect the active scientific collaborations between the different project partners.

The video has the following storyline: First, the **BioCombs4Nanofibers project**, its name, the European frame and all partners are introduced. Subsequently, industrial applications (**ELMARCO**) are pointed out and the general project aim for producing technical surfaces being antiadhesive for nanofibers is motivated. In a next step, the project inspiring idea of nature’s solution evolutionary realized for cribellate spiders (**RWTH**) is presented, revealing the characteristically nanostructured surface of the calamistrum of the garden center spider (*Uloborus plumipes*) [1,2]. This idea of a surface being antiadhesive for spider silk nanofibers is then transferred to other applications such as the development of anti-bacterial surfaces [3]. For detailing this project idea, the microscopic appearance of bacteria, their nanofiber cell-appendages, and their collective formation of biofilms on surfaces are presented. Everyday life relevance of biofilm-related problems in dishwashers or antibiotic resistances in medicine are explained. A technical solution can be provided by surface nanotexturing through *laser-induced periodic surface structures* (LIPSS) that are explored at **BAM**, **JKU**, and **FORTH**. The successful mimicking of such nanostructures on commercial plastic (PET) foils (**JKU**) with a bacterial repellence of > 90% (**BAM**) [3] is proven at the end of the video.

The videorecording with audio track was created by **BAM** through MS PowerPoint and exhibits a total duration of 6:06 minutes. It uses project internal material provided by the project partners. Some external resources such as free cliparts (<https://openclipart.org>) and an animated video-gif-image (provided by the University of Twente, The Netherlands) were used. All sources and references are listed at the end of the video along with a funding acknowledgement statement, creators' information and contact addresses.

A screenshot from the video (at 3:34 min) is shown in the following:

BioCombs4Nanofibers

Spider legs offer the solution!

RWTH AACHEN
UNIVERSITY

https://download.jku.at/org/7kM/xyU/BioCombs4Nanofibers/D5.6_video%20for%20the%20broader%20public_23.03.2022.mp4

References:

[1] A.-C. Joel, M. Meyer, J. Heitz, A. Heiss, D. Park, H. Adamova, W. Baumgartner, "Biomimetic Combs as Antiadhesive Tools to Manipulate Nanofibers". ACS Appl. Nano Mater. **3** (2020), 3395–3401, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsanm.0c00130>
(Open Access, CC-BY-NC-ND)

[2] M. Meyer, G. Buchberger, J. Heitz, D. Baiko, A.-C. Joel, "Ambient climate influences anti-adhesion between biomimetic structured foil and nanofibers", Nanomaterials **11** (2021), 3222, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano11123222>
(Open Access, CC-BY 4.0)

[3] A.M. Richter, G. Buchberger, D. Stifter, J. Duchoslav, A. Hertwig, J. Bonse, J. Heitz, K. Schwibbert, "Spatial period of laser-induced surface nanoripples on PET determines Escherichia coli repellence", Nanomaterials **11** (2021), 3000, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano11113000>
(Open Access, CC-BY 4.0)

2. Evaluation of Goals and Resulting Actions

The video of this report is a public document (MP4) which has been uploaded to the streaming server video.jku.at of **JKU** and can be downloaded under the link:

https://download.jku.at/org/7kM/xyU/BioCombs4Nanofibers/D5.6_video%20for%20the%20broader%20public_23.03.2022.mp4

This link will be included in the dissemination section of the web-site of the **BioCombs4Nanofibers project** (<http://biocombs4nanofibers.eu>) under the title “Video for broader public: From Nanofibers over Spiders to Bacteria” and shared on the projects **ResearchGate** profile (<https://www.researchgate.net/project/BioCombs4Nanofibers-Antiadhensive-Bionic-Combs-for-Handling-of-Nanofibers-EU-HORIZON-2020>) and on **ZENODO** (<https://zenodo.org/communities/biocombs4nanofibers/>). Moreover, it will be disseminated via **Twitter** (<https://twitter.com/biocombs4nano>).